

**FACTORS AFFECTING THE INTERLANGUAGE PRAGMATIC (ILP)
COMPETENCE OF GRADE 11-TVL CAREGIVING STUDENTS:
BASIS FOR CRAFTING AN ILP COMPETENCE
REINFORCEMENT MODEL**

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Factors Affecting the Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) Competence of Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students: Basis for Crafting an ILP Competence Reinforcement Model

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Abstract

This study focuses on the Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) competence levels of Grade 11-TVL Caregiving students and the factors influencing these levels. Additionally, it aimed to develop an ILP Reinforcement Model to enhance the ILP Competence of the said students. The study employed a mixed-method research design and utilized an Oral Discourse Completion Task (ODCT) to assess the ILP Competence of the participants. The findings revealed that the students excelled in Expressive speech acts, achieving an overall ILP competence rating of 5, indicating "Excellence." In Directives, Commissives, and Assertives, they received an overall rating of 4, signifying a "Good" level of competence. Various teaching methods were employed to aid in assessing their ILP competence, with the combination of the Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and the Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT) emerging as the most effective instructional and assessment method. Furthermore, an ILP Reinforcement Model was developed to address identified gaps in the study. This model comprises five stages: Pragmalinguistic Input, Instructional Methods, Pragmatic Filter, Learner's Developing System, and Pragmalinguistic Output. Its primary goal is to establish a connection between pragmalinguistic input and practical application in real-world scenarios for Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students, with a focus on speech acts of Directives, Commissives, and Assertives. A noteworthy finding from the study underscores the importance of a balanced approach to teaching ILP, which fosters a comprehensive and immersive learning environment for the students. This holistic approach involves not only addressing the technical aspects of ILP but also integrating sociocultural and pragmatic dimensions to provide a more effective and contextually relevant ILP education.

Keywords: *Interlanguage Pragmatics, speech acts, illocutionary acts, expressives, assertives, Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) Competence Model*

Introduction

In the country, the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) strand in Grade 11 prepares students for technical and vocational careers. Many students who complete this strand aspire to work abroad to advance their careers and improve their living conditions. However, they may face challenges in securing jobs overseas, especially if they lack the necessary second language (L2) skills.

The Department of Education (DepEd) acknowledges the significance of fostering students' communicative competence, encompassing speaking and listening skills, in diverse contexts to produce graduates who are competent in global communication. This is evident through the intended learning outcomes in the Oral Communication subject, which is taught to Grade 11 students in Senior High Schools (SHS). The subject covers various topics, including the recognition of appropriate social contexts for different speech styles, engagement in conversations using respectful and effective communication strategies, and the application of principles for delivering speeches effectively in different situations (Department of Education, 2013).

These learning outcomes prioritize the development of Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) competence, which plays a vital role for second language learners in understanding and being understood by speakers of the same language and/or native speakers with different cultural, regional, or social backgrounds because it involves the negotiation of meaning within specific settings.

However, in ILP, language learners often find it challenging to comprehend native speakers' messages in both spoken and written forms. Simply acquiring vocabulary and grammar is insufficient for effective communication; understanding pragmatics is crucial. Various factors, such as geography, politics, and culture, make it difficult for students to accurately interpret meanings, resulting in confusion and misunderstandings during interactions in the target language (Ashraf & Ali, 2021).

Moreover, deviating from pragmatic norms can exacerbate pre-existing biases about the culture or ethnicity of specific groups. Despite the well-established connection between Second Language Acquisition (SLA) and pragmatics, SLA research has often overlooked the study of pragmatics. Grammatical accuracy by itself is not enough for effective communication; understanding the context of a situation is also crucial. This underscores ongoing issues in how Oral Communication in Context is taught to learners, particularly Interlanguage Pragmatics (ILP), a component of communicative competence within Oral Communication (Choraih et al., 2016). These research findings highlight the urgent need to incorporate the sociocultural rules of the target language into English language instruction.

Additionally, employers in foreign countries frequently require a high level of English proficiency, acknowledging it as the global language of business and communication. Although students in the TVL strand receive English as a Second Language (ESL) instruction, this may not sufficiently prepare them to meet the cultural and linguistic demands of the international job market.

In the Senior High School (SHS) curriculum, particularly Grade 11 students, there is an explicit focus on enhancing oral communication

and social competence (DepEd, 2013). According to Pregoner and Nabuya (2019), the development of social skills holds significant importance for effective collaboration, fostering positive relationships, resolving conflicts, and mastering other vital aspects relevant to vocational fields that demand teamwork, customer service, and cooperation among colleagues. Proficiency in intercultural communication necessitates an understanding of grammatical structures and, most importantly, the ability to apply language skills effectively in real social contexts.

Nonetheless, studies suggest that although individuals graduating from TVL programs may possess the necessary technical expertise for their roles, they might face challenges in effectively communicating with colleagues and clients in international settings. This difficulty could be attributed to a lack of social interaction knowledge and intercultural language proficiency. The skills emphasized in the program may not align with the demands of the global job market, leaving graduates without the critical language proficiencies and other essential skill sets for international employment.

Linguistic mistakes made by learners can be seen as harmless errors, but pragmatic mistakes are more challenging to justify. Pragmatic failures can lead to confusion, misunderstandings, and communication breakdowns, and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners may be stereotyped as insensitive, impolite, or inept.

In Bognuyan National High School (Boghai), language teachers have observed that Grade-11 students face challenges in developing their interlanguage pragmatic abilities. They often encounter difficulties in effectively and appropriately navigating social interactions, both within and outside the classroom. During class discussions, these students often struggle to employ suitable speech styles and communication strategies that align with the context and audience. This can unintentionally lead to them coming across as either overly formal, which might seem insincere, or overly informal and possibly impolite, leading to misunderstandings among their peers and even their teachers. This not only hampers effective communication but also hinders the establishment of a conducive and harmonious learning environment.

Given these challenging circumstances, this study aims to explore language teachers' observations by assessing the Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) Competence of Grade 11 students, specifically within the TVL Caregiving strand. The goal is to identify factors influencing their current ILP competence. This investigation is crucial as their future careers will require strong interpersonal communication skills and ILP proficiency to improve service delivery. Drawing from Hardjati and Febrianita's (2019) insights, which highlighted the importance of interpersonal communication skills and understanding speech acts in professional settings, the researcher recognizes the need for a localized study of ILP.

In line with this endeavor, another study, conducted by Purwaningsih and Pratama (2020), emphasizes the importance of intercultural communication in caregiver-elderly interactions, particularly in clinical practice. It underscores that elderly-centered communication is fundamental to providing high-quality patient care, which, in turn, facilitates treatment planning through the effective transmission of information and fosters a therapeutic and supportive environment for the elderly.

Furthermore, this research aims to prepare Grade-11 TVL Caregiving students, specifically for potential job opportunities abroad, by evaluating their level of ILP Competence and identifying the underlying factors that influence it. Additionally, the study intends to develop an ILP Reinforcement Model that will serve as a guide for restructuring instructional and assessment methods and implementing effective and authentic pedagogical approaches, specifically designed to teach ILP to Grade 11-TVL Caregiving students, equipping them with the necessary skills for their future professions.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the level of ILP competence of Grade 11-TVL students and investigate the factors that contribute to these levels. By doing so, this study aimed to enhance the student's preparedness for future employment opportunities overseas. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) competence of the Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students?
2. What are the instructional methods used in teaching ILP to them?
3. What are the outcomes of their ILP Competence considering the instructional methods employed during the assessment and the type of learner they are?
4. What model could be developed based on the results of the study?

Methodology

Participants

This study examines a group of 38 Grade 11 Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Caregiving students currently taking the Oral Communication in Context course at Bognuyan National High School (Boghai) in Bognuyan, Gasan, Marinduque. These students were selected because of the critical role that intercultural communication and interlanguage pragmatics play in the caregiving profession.

Moreover, the caregiving profession requires effective communication with diverse groups, including elderly residents from various cultural backgrounds. Mastery of intercultural communication and interlanguage pragmatics is crucial for the well-being of both

caregivers and care recipients. This study selected caregiving students as respondents to enhance their communication skills, particularly in ILP Competence, deepen their understanding of cultural nuances when interacting with elderly patients, and improve the overall quality of care they provide.

Instruments

As instruments for determining the caregiving students' level of ILP competence, an Oral Discourse Completion Task (ODCT) composed of 40 life-based situations was modified from the instrument of Alzeebaree (2017). It was integrated into the Speech Acts (Illocutionary Act) lesson of the Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students and audio-recorded by the subject teacher for data authenticity. The results of the said audio recording were analyzed and interpreted by the researcher also employing the Coding Framework of Glaser and Strauss (1967). Thereby, the overall results of the analysis and interpretations made were used to craft an ILP model. Furthermore, to determine the instructional methods for teaching ILP, an interview with the Oral Communication teacher concerned was conducted.

According to Barron (2019), ODCT is the best tool for producing sufficiently large corpora of comparable, systematically varied speech act data. Because they can be translated into any language and distributed to large groups of informants in a short period of time, ODCTs are ideal for the contrastive study of speech acts. Thereafter, the data/responses gathered from the ODCT were transcribed, analyzed, and interpreted using the Coding Framework of (Glaser & Strauss, 1967).

Procedure

The study's instrument (ODCT) underwent thorough validation by language experts. Upon approval, the researcher collaborated with both the school principal of Boghai as well as the Oral Communication teacher concerned. The researcher enlisted the assistance of the teacher to carry out an audio recording while integrating the Oral Discourse Completion Task (ODCT) into the lesson on Illocutionary Acts. Additionally, an interview was conducted with the Oral Communication teacher to explore the instructional methods employed in teaching Illocutionary Acts to the students.

Ethical Considerations

All data and information obtained and collected were treated with the highest discretion. The study was also guided by ethical considerations such as: (1) the respondents' dignity, rights, and well-being were protected during the study; (2) the respondent may leave questions unanswered if he/she feels offended; (3) the respondents' responses to each prompt were only used during the research time frame, and; (4) prior to the audio recording, permission was also obtained from the Principal of Bognuyan National High School. Furthermore, before starting the data-gathering procedure, the researcher ensured that the study's goals and objectives were clearly communicated to the principal and the oral communication teacher concerned. All data gathered and audio-recorded were solely used to determine the study's findings.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the research findings derived from the collected data, offering an overview of the study's outcomes and in-depth discussions of both quantitative and qualitative data. The data were obtained from the Oral Discourse Completion Tasks (ODCT) to assess the level of ILP competence among Grade 11 TVL - Caregiving students in Boghai, as well as to analyze the factors influencing these levels and the types of learners they are. Additionally, an interview was conducted with the oral communication teacher to determine the instructional methods used in teaching illocutionary speech acts to these students.

Level of Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) Competence of the Grade 11 TVL - Caregiving Students

Through analyzing the responses collected from the modified and adapted Oral Discourse Completion Task (ODCT) of Alzeebaree (2017), the level of Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) Competence of the Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students in Boghai is hereby identified and presented as outlined in Table 1.

Additionally, the mentioned ODCT comprises 40 real-life scenarios, categorized into the four (4) Types of Illocutionary Speech Acts (Directives, Commissives, Expressives, and Assertives), which were carefully selected to ensure their relevance and relatability to Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students. These scenarios were also validated by English Language experts to ensure their appropriateness. The questions were then incorporated into the students' Oral Communication in Context class. During this process, the students provided verbal responses to the scenarios, with their oral communication teacher recording their responses. They were also encouraged to respond as they would act in real-life situations.

Four Selected Illocutionary Speech Acts to Examine the Students' Level of ILP Competence

According to Haucsa et al. (2020) Illocutionary Speech Acts were categorized into five classes, namely, Directives, Commissives, Expressives, Assertives, and Declarations. Yet only four were selected due to their common usage in cross-cultural communication and relevance to the caregiving profession. Directives may involve instructing or guiding care-related tasks, Commissives may relate to promises or commitments in caregiving contexts, Expressives may express empathy or emotions, and Assertives may be used to convey information about a patient's condition or treatment.

Their scopes were expounded as follows:

1. Directives are used to request, command, suggest, or advise someone to perform a specific action. They are designed to influence the behavior of the listener and are often framed as imperatives or interrogatives. Common examples include commands, orders, requests, and suggestions.
2. Commissives are speech acts in which the speaker expresses their commitment or intention to carry out a future action. They involve the speaker making a promise, giving a threat, expressing a refusal, or offering a pledge. It also deals with actions the speaker is committed to performing.
3. Expressives convey the speaker's emotional or psychological state, feelings, or attitudes. They are used to express emotions, such as joy, sorrow, pleasure, pain, like, dislike, and so on. They are primarily concerned with the speaker's inner experiences and emotional responses.
4. Assertives aim to convey information about facts, beliefs, or statements regarding the external world. They are used to assert or describe what the speaker believes to be true or false. They also deal with propositions and the representation of reality.

Table 1. *Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students in terms of Directives (Requests)*

Learner	Rating	Description	Mean	Indicators
2	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	May I borrow a book?
3	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Hey, tita, can I ask for a favor? Can you help me arrange my stuff?
5	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Hi, Sir, can you lower your voice because I'm distracted?
6	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Hi, May I borrow your pen?
7	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Hi, may I ask when are you free? I just want to have some chitchats with you.
4	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Hey, Mister, can I ask you to stand up and can I sit?
1	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Hey, Waiter, where is my order?
8	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Hi, Sir, can I ask you to sit there because I already ordered?
9	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Can you get me that?
10	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Hi, sir, I want to change my session because I want to learn something.
	4	Good	3.50-4.49	Overall Rating

Table 1 shows the Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students in terms of Directives (Requests).

As illustrated in the table, the respondents exhibit varying levels of ILP Competence in Directives speech acts, ranging from "Fair" to "Excellent," with mean values ranging from 2.50-3.49 to 4.50-5.00. The highest level of ILP Competence is attributed to 5 students namely learners 2, 3, 5, 6, and 7 who have an almost perfectly appropriate and effective level of directness, politeness, and formality based on the Appropriateness Rating Scale for Pragmatic Speaking Tasks developed by (Taguchi, 2019). Notably, the Overall ILP Competence of the students in Directives is rated as "GOOD," with a Composite Mean of 3.50-4.49.

Based on Taguchi's (2019) Appropriateness Rating Scale for Pragmatic Speaking Tasks, achieving a Good Overall ILP Competence suggests that caregiving students possess proficiency or competency in their pragmatic language skills. They exhibit a level of proficiency that is sufficiently appropriate in terms of directness, politeness, and formality in their verbal expressions.

The Good level of ILP competence among caregiving students might stem from their frequent encounters with requests in everyday interactions. In such situations, individuals often try to persuade others to act or respond to their demands, requests, or hints. This observation is supported by Azhari and Nuriadi (2018), who note that second language speakers typically find direct strategies for making requests easy to handle, as they often resemble patterns in their native languages.

Table 1.1. *Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students in terms of Commissives (Promises/Offers)*

Learners	Rating	Description	Mean	Commissives Type	Indicators
11	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Offer	Hey, leader, can I take the responsibility of drawing and do it in my home?
12	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	Best friend, I'm sorry I will not attend your party, I promise, I will attend to our outing.
14	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	I can go tomorrow, 10 A.M.
15	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	Sorry, guys, I'm late, but I'll come early to our next meeting.
16	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	Friend, sorry, I accidentally broke your laptop, and I will buy another one and replace it.
18	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	I'm sorry for not attending our family reunion, I promise, I will host the next reunion.
17	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Offer	I can help you with planting.
13	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Offer	I will volunteer for a charity.
19	4	Good	3.50-4.49	Promise	I want to help the community campaign and I will donate every month.

20	4	Good	3.50-4.49	Offer	Hey, leader, can I use the computer to do the PowerPoint?
	4	Good	3.50-4.49	Overall Rating	

Table 1.1 shows the Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students in terms of Commissives (Promises/Offers). As depicted in Table 1.1, the participants exhibit varying degrees of ILP Competence in the Commissive speech acts, ranging from "Fair" to "Excellent," with mean scores ranging from 2.50-3.49 and 4.50-5.00. Specifically, six (6) learners, namely 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, and 18, attained an "Excellent" rating in their ILP Competence assessment. Notably, the findings revealed an overall "GOOD" rating for their ILP Competence level, with a Composite Mean of 3.50-4.49.

According to Taguchi's (2019) Appropriateness Rating Scale for Pragmatic Speaking Tasks, attaining a Good Overall ILP Competence indicates that caregiving students possess proficiency or competency in their pragmatic language skills. They demonstrate a level of proficiency that is adequately suitable in terms of directness, politeness, and formality in their verbal expressions.

The Good overall ILP competence demonstrated by caregiving suggests that they have a solid grasp of social norms and expectations surrounding promises and offers. They are able to navigate interpersonal interactions skillfully, considering factors such as politeness, context, and the needs of the listener. This may be due to the demands of their profession, which require them to cultivate skills such as pledging commitments to the individuals under their care. This notion finds backing in the findings of Ashfiya and Degaf (2023), who posit that promises represent declarations wherein the speaker expresses their duty to fulfill a specific action in the future. These pledges serve as verbal commitments made by one person to another.

Table 1.2. Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students in terms of Expressives (Apologies/Gratitude)

Learner	Rating	Description	Mean	Expressive Types	Indicators
21	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Apology	Hey, I'm sorry, I didn't mean to throw the coffee on your table, please forgive me.
22	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Gratitude	Thank you for helping me move to my new apartment.
23	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Apology	Sorry, my friend, I didn't attend your birthday party, I promise, I'll treat you next time.
24	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Apology	Brother, I'm sorry, I scratched your car.
25	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Gratitude	Sorry, Sir, I didn't pass my assignment on time. I will pass my assignment tomorrow.
26	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Gratitude	Thank you, my little sister, for giving me a present for this day. I appreciate it very much.
27	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Gratitude	I'm sorry, Rafael, for being late, can I just make it up to you by giving you a present or something?
	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Overall Rating	

Table 1.2 shows the Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students in terms of Expressives (Apologies/Gratitude).

As shown in Table 1.2, the respondents displayed an "EXCELLENT" Overall ILP Competence in the Speech Acts of Expressives, with mean values of 4.50-5.00. Remarkably, all seven (7) students gained the highest degree of ILP Competence showing that they exhibit an almost perfectly appropriate and effective level of directness, politeness, and formality based on the Appropriateness Rating Scale for Pragmatic Speaking Tasks established by (Taguchi, 2019).

The Excellent level of competence among caregiving students may stem from their training for their future roles as caregivers, which fosters politeness, particularly in interactions with those under their care. This is supported by Ogiermann and Bella (2021), who states that, unlike other speech acts, Expressives primarily serve interpersonal functions. They are inherently polite and supportive of the listener, performing relational work that manifests as either formulaic acts of courtesy or genuine expressions of emotion.

Table 1.3. *Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students in terms of Assertives (Statements/Facts/Opinions)*

Learner	Rating	Description	Mean	Assertives Type	Indicators
29	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Opinion	The movie Darna is so funny.
30	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Statement	I learned in Oral Comm. that 90% of the time we use non-verbal communication.
31	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Fact	The Spaniards colonized the Philippines.
28	1	Very poor	1-1.49	Fact	I disagree in death penalty because no opinion.
32	4	Good	3.50-4.49	Statement	Hi, Sir, I work in Marelco for 4 years.
	4	Good	4.50-5.00	Overall Rating	

Table 1.3 shows the Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students in terms of Assertives (Statements/Facts/Opinions).

As illustrated in Table 3.3, the findings indicate that respondents display varying levels of ILP Competence in Assertive speech acts, ranging from "Very Poor" to "Excellent," with mean values between 1-1.49 and 4.50-5.00. Specifically, learners 29, 30, and 31 achieved an Excellent ILP rating, learner 4 attained a Good rating, however, learner 28 received a Very Poor ILP competence rating. The lowest level of ILP Competence is attributed to student/s stating expressions that are very difficult or too little to understand and when there is no evidence that the intended speech acts are performed, as assessed using the Appropriateness Rating Scale for Pragmatic Speaking Tasks developed by (Taguchi, 2019). Significantly, the overall ILP Competence of the students in Directives is categorized as "GOOD," with a Composite Mean of 3.50-4.49. According to Taguchi's (2019) Appropriateness Rating Scale for Pragmatic Speaking Tasks, achieving a Good Overall ILP Competence signifies that caregiving students have proficient pragmatic language skills. They exhibit a level of proficiency that is suitably appropriate in terms of directness, politeness, and formality in their verbal expressions.

However, one student demonstrated Very Poor ILP competence in stating a "Fact." This may be attributed to the cognitive load associated with expressing his opinion on the death penalty, as he lacks sufficient schema to support his stance on the issue. According to Paas et al. (2020), when learning complex new tasks, learners utilize the majority of their working memory resources in the process. This results in a substantial extraneous cognitive load, consequently leaving insufficient resources for effective learning. Similarly, when a student is required to state a "fact," especially on a complex topic such as death penalty, they must draw upon both linguistic knowledge and cognitive processing to ensure the accuracy and relevance of their statement. This dual demand can create a significant extraneous cognitive load. If the student lacks sufficient schema or background knowledge on the topic, the cognitive load becomes even higher, as they must simultaneously process the content and structure of their language.

Instructional Methods Employed in the Assessment of Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving Students' ILP Competence

In an interview with the Oral Communication teacher in Boghai, he outlined the three primary instructional methods—Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT), and Grammar Translation Method (GTM)—that he employed to teach ILP to his students. He explained that these methods were chosen deliberately to aid him in assessing the ILP Competence level of his Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students due to specific reasons. He opted for Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) to foster a communicative and interactive environment, believing it would enhance the students' practical language skills. The Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT) was chosen to provide structured support, facilitating a gradual progression in the development of ILP Competence. Finally, the Grammar Translation Method (GTM) was utilized to ensure a comprehensive understanding of linguistic structures, contributing to a solid foundation in language proficiency. Through these carefully chosen instructional methods, the teacher aimed to holistically evaluate the ILP Competence of his Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

He highlighted that using Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) to teach Speech Acts—an area within Oral Communication in Context—and to assess his students' ILP competence is particularly effective, given the specific requirements for "English language learning" in this subject. The primary focus is on communicating in the target language. Hien (2021) supported this, noting that a central feature of CLT is its emphasis on learning to communicate in the target language.

CLT also taps into the social dimension of language which is considered the central aspect of ILP. It promotes interactive and cooperative learning, enabling the Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students to engage in localized and contextualized group activities, discussions, and collaborative projects. "Through these interactions, students can observe and practice the complexities of politeness, indirect speech acts, and other pragmatic features," he added. This was proven by Hien (2021), that CLT is one of the most effective methods in "teaching and learning" a second language because it provides opportunities for learners to practice and improve their communicative competence in pedagogic and real-life situations.

As Santosa (2020) points out, the principles of CLT are in harmony with the concept of Speech Acts, and this alignment serves as a primary reason for the teacher's utilization of it in teaching Interlanguage Pragmatics in Oral Communication in Context. Moreover, CLT places a significant emphasis on communicative competence rather than solely focusing on grammatical proficiency. The teacher's instructional approach resonates with the theory of communicative competence, particularly emphasizing the concept of actional

competence. Notably, this aspect of communicative competence is closely intertwined with speech acts, as further emphasized by (Santosa, 2020).

Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)

In Oral Communication instruction, the teacher employs the Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT) to guide his students and assess their ILP Competence. This involves offering prompts to assist students in formulating appropriate responses in diverse scenarios. Scaffolding, in the field of education, is a method that provides transient support, direction, and structure to learners as they acquire new skills and knowledge. According to Sarmiento-Campos et al. (2022), the adoption of scaffolding as an instructional strategy has gained substantial popularity in recent years, particularly in language teaching. Initially rooted in the construction industry, the concept of scaffolding has evolved and expanded to encompass supportive instruction across various disciplines. This transformation has been spurred by a range of learning theories, encouraging educators in EFL (English as a Foreign Language) and ESL (English as a Second Language) to incorporate innovative techniques into their teaching methodologies.

To this day, Lev Vygotsky's Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT) remains practically relevant in ESL classrooms, especially in teaching Interlanguage Pragmatics (ILP) in Boghai. This approach emphasizes the interdependence of learning and development in facilitating language acquisition. In the Explicit SCT approach, the Oral Communication teacher assumes the role of providing temporary assistance to students as they engage in tasks, rather than leaving them to work in isolation. This pedagogical method nurtures a positive learning environment, where students are encouraged to seek solutions, support their peers, and express their viewpoints, thereby bolstering their confidence as they tackle more demanding assignments.

Grammar Translation Method (GTM)

Another method employed by the teacher of Oral Communication in teaching ILP as well as in assessing his students' level of ILP Competence is the Grammar Translation Method (GTM). He considers this method to be particularly useful, especially in the Public Education system, where strict adherence to English-only policies may not be consistently enforced and is only practiced in Science Classes. He points out that Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students often encounter difficulties in directly expressing their thoughts from their native language to English. In class recitations, he often encounters manifestations of language anxiety (i.e., anxiousness, and trembling). As a result, he resorts to translating English questions and tasks into Filipino, and similarly, he translates his learners' Filipino/Tagalog responses into English to facilitate their comprehension and expression.

The GTM, known for its collaborative thinking-aloud technique, has been affirmed as an effective instructional approach for teaching ILP (Derakhshan et al., 2020). The method encourages learners to participate in guided practice with their teacher. According to the Oral Communication instructor, when presented with oral tasks and activities, his Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students enthusiastically embrace translation, leading to increased engagement and enhanced ILP competence. This interactive approach cultivates a dynamic learning environment that facilitates the development of ILP competence among these students.

Grade 11-TVL Caregiving Students' ILP Competence Considering the Instructional Methods Employed by their Subject Teacher during the ILP Assessment and the Type of Learner they are

As illustrated in Table 2, the participants showcase a range of proficiency levels in ILP Competence in terms of Directive speech acts. This spectrum extends from "Fair" to "Excellent," culminating an overall evaluation of students' ILP Competence in Directives as "Good," with a Composite Mean ranging from 3.50-4.49. However, it is crucial to also acknowledge the influence of the instructional method/s employed in the assessments and to consider the nature of the learners to discern how these factors contributed to their ILP Competence Levels. The Oral Communication teacher categorized learners into three groups: Type A, denoting fast learners; Type B, representing average learners; and Type C, indicating slow learners.

Type A Learners

Subsequently, Learner 7, classified as a Type A learner, was presented with ODCT based solely on the principles of Communicative Language Teaching (CLT), resulting in a rating of 5 (Excellent) within the range of 4.50-5.00., corresponding to an ILP continuum level of 90%-100%. This indicates a Near-Native/Proficient level, meaning the learner uses a second language almost as well as a native speaker. In contrast, Learner 4 was taught using a combination of CLT and the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), achieving a rating of 3 (Fair) within the range of 2.50-3.49, corresponding to an ILP continuum level of 50% - 70%. This indicates an Upper-Intermediate level, meaning somewhat appropriate in directness, politeness, and formality and expressions are more direct or indirect than required.

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) places a strong focus on functionality and communication over strict grammar. In CLT, the primary goal is to enable learners to use the language effectively in real-life situations, emphasizing practical communication skills. This could explain why Learner 7, who received an ODCT prompt exclusively based on CLT principles, may have had more opportunities for authentic communication in the target language, contributing to his/her 5 or "Excellent" level of ILP Competence. These findings are supported by Toro et al. (2019), which underscores the significance of teachers consistently encouraging students' communicative competence. In addition to recognizing students' language proficiency limitations, educators should establish environments that facilitate interactions and involve learners in spoken activities, ultimately enhancing their capacity to effectively use

the target language.

In contrast, Learner 4's performance might have been affected by the challenge of balancing the competing priorities between CLT and the Grammar Translation Method (GTM). CLT encourages learners to focus on conveying meaning and understanding, while the Grammar Translation Method (GTM) has a greater focus on precision in language use. It is possible that the combination of these methodologies confused Learner 4, resulting in his/her 3 or "Fair" level of ILP Competence. This outcome could be connected to the insights from Omar (2019), which highlight that GTM places a strong focus on grammar and vocabulary, often at the expense of nurturing effective communication skills. Consequently, students may excel in understanding grammatical rules in the second language (L2), but they may encounter challenges in communicating effectively in that language.

Table 2. Level of ILP Competence for Directives (Requests), Instructional Methods Employed, and Learner Types

Learner	Type of Learner	Method Used	Rating	Description	Mean	Indicators
5	Type B	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Hi, Sir, can you lower your voice because I'm distracted?
6	Type B	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Hi, May I borrow your pen?
7	Type A	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Hi, may I ask when are you free? I just want to have some chitchats with you.
2	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	May I borrow a book?
3	Type C	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Hey, tita, can I ask for a favor? Can you help me arrange my stuff?
1	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Hey, Waiter, where is my order?
4	Type A	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Hey, Mister, can I ask you to stand up and can I sit?
8	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Hi, Sir, can I ask you to sit there because I already ordered?
9	Type B	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Can you get me that?
10	Type B	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Hi, sir, I want to change my session because I want to learn something.
4			GOOD	3.50-4.49	OVERALL RATING	

Legend:

- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)
- Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)
- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Grammar Translation Method (GTM)
- Grammar Translation Method (GTM)

Type B Learners

Among the four students categorized as Type B Learners, Learners 5 and 6 were presented with ODC T prompts following the principles of the CLT method, both achieving an ILP Competence rating of 5 (Excellent), corresponding to a 90% - 100% ILP continuum level. This suggests a Near-Native/Proficient level, signifying that the learner uses a second language almost as well as a native speaker. In contrast, Learners 9 and 10, who were exposed to ODC T prompts utilizing the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), attained an ILP Competence rating of 3 (Fair), corresponding to a 50% - 70% ILP continuum level. This indicates an Upper-Intermediate level, demonstrating that the learner uses L2 more frequently with fewer L1-influenced errors. Individual learners display different learning styles and preferences. It is likely that Learners 5 and 6 were better suited to the interactive and communicative approach of CLT, while Learners 9 and 10 might have benefited more from alternative methods for assessing ILP Competence, other than the GTM, that aligned better with their personal learning preferences. These preferences significantly influence their performance. This aligns with Omar's (2019) findings, which describe how students in certain countries learned English by memorizing vocabulary, studying grammar, translating passages, and occasionally practicing conversational phrases. Although these students focused on language study, this method might not have matched their learning styles and preferences, possibly leading to their limited proficiency in listening, speaking,

and using the language in real-life situations outside the classroom.

Type C Learners

Four learners were identified as Type C. Learners 1 and 8 were presented with ODC T prompts following the principles of the Grammar Translation Method (GTM), both achieving a rating of 3 (Fair), corresponding to a 50% - 70% ILP continuum level. This indicates an Upper-Intermediate level, indicating that the learner uses L2 more frequently with fewer L1-influenced errors. In contrast, Learner 2 received an ODC T prompt using the combination of Explicit SCT and GTM methods, resulting in an ILP Competence rating of 5 (Excellent), corresponding to a 90% - 100% ILP continuum level. This proposes a Near-Native/Proficient level, signifying that the learner uses a second language almost as well as a native speaker.

Lastly, Learner 3 was provided with an ODC T prompt delivered using a combination of CLT and GTM, also achieving a rating of 5 (Excellent), corresponding to a 90% - 100% ILP continuum level. This also proposes a Near-Native/Proficient level, showing that the learner uses a second language almost as well as a native speaker.

Learners 1 and 8 received ODC T prompts following GTM, which emphasizes precision in language and grammatical accuracy. The "Fair" rating might be due to the potential challenge of meeting GTM's high standards for linguistic accuracy, which can be demanding for learners. This method may not provide as much opportunity for practical communication, which could explain the lower rating. Additionally, Learner 2's "Excellent" rating could result from the combination of Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT) and GTM. Explicit SCT focuses on providing structured support and guidance and can help learners understand how language functions in context. This blend may have struck a balance between linguistic accuracy and practical use, which contributed to the "Excellent" rating. Furthermore, Learner 3's high rating, like Learner 2, can be attributed to the combination of CLT and GTM. CLT, with its focus on functional communication, would have encouraged the learner to understand language in real-life situations. The integration of GTM for accuracy may have created a well-rounded learning experience, leading to an "Excellent" rating. The research carried out by Kim & Baig (2021), corroborates the findings of the present study. They argue that CLT proves to be a superior approach because it incorporates various activities and fosters the active involvement of students in the learning process. Additionally, it also aligns with the current results, expressing the perspective that while GTM is effective in teaching English grammar, a combination of GTM and CLT can yield even better results as per (Kim & Baig, 2021).

Table 2.1. Level of ILP Competence for Commissives (Promises/Offer s), Instructional Employed, and Learner Types

Learners	Type of Learner	Method Used	Rating	Description	Mean	Commissives Type	Indicators
11	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Offer	Hey, leader, can I take the responsibility of drawing and do it in my home?
12	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	Best friend, I'm sorry I will not attend your party, I promise, I will attend to our outing.
18	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	I'm sorry for not attending to our family reunion, I promise, I will host the next reunion.
14	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	I can go tomorrow, 10 A.M.
15	Type B	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	Sorry, guys, I'm late, but I'll come early to our next meeting.
16	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Promise	Friend, sorry, I accidentally broke your laptop, and I will buy another one and replace it.
13	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Offer	I will volunteer for a charity.
17	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	3	Fair	2.50-3.49	Offer	I can help you with planting.
19	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	4	Good	3.50-4.49	Promise	I want to help the community campaign and I will donate every month.
20	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	4	Good	3.50-4.49	Offer	Hey, leader, can I use the computer to do the PowerPoint?
			4	GOOD	3.50-4.49	OVERALL RATING	

Legend:

- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)
- Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)
- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Grammar Translation Method (GTM)
- Grammar Translation Method (GTM)

As outlined in Table 2.1, the respondents demonstrate a spectrum of ILP Competence in Commissive speech acts, encompassing levels from "Fair" to "Excellent."

The overall ILP Competence rating in Commissives stands at "Good," with a Composite Mean within the 3.50-4.49 range. With these findings, it is also imperative to recognize the impact of the instructional methods employed in the assessments and to contemplate the characteristics of the learners. Understanding how these factors contributed to their ILP Competence Levels is crucial for a comprehensive evaluation of their ILP Competence rating.

The responses in Commissive speech acts were categorized based on the types of learners who underwent assessment, including Type B (Average learners) and Type C (Slow learners). Notably, no learners classified as Type A (Fast learners) were assessed within this speech act.

Type B Learners

Learner 15 belonging to Type B, who underwent evaluation utilizing the GTM, achieved an "Excellent" rating with scores ranging from 4.50-5.00 corresponding to a 90% - 100% ILP continuum level which suggests Near-Native/Proficient level, signifying that the learner uses a second language almost as well as a native speaker. This outcome can be attributed to the learner's possession of a higher level of language proficiency and the suitability of the GTM, which could have allowed him/her to excel in the assessment. A strong command of the language is frequently linked to enhanced performance in the ODCT. Eisa (2020) stated that the primary benefit of the GTM lies in its ability to comprehend diverse phraseology, allowing for smooth translation and a deeper grasp of complex concepts. This contributes to its continued global prevalence, supported by the absence of a language barrier between students and teachers, promoting effective communication in the student's mother tongue.

Type C Learners

Learners 11, 14, and 16, categorized as Type C learners were assessed by their Oral Communication teacher using the GTM, they achieved a rating of 5 (Excellent) with a range of 4.50-5.00. 00 corresponding to a 90% - 100% ILP continuum level which suggests Near-Native/Proficient level, signifying that the learner uses a second language almost as well as a native speaker. In contrast, learners 13 and 17 who underwent assessment with the use of GTM received a rating of 3 (Fair) with a range of 2.50-3.49 which corresponds to 50% - 70% continuum level indicating an Upper-Intermediate learner, which has a somewhat appropriate in the level of directness, politeness, and formality. Expressions may be more direct or indirect than the situation requires, based on the Interlanguage Continuum of Tanvir.

The performance differences among Type C learners, with three earning an "Excellent" rating and two receiving a "Fair" rating through a GTM assessment, can be attributed to several underlying factors. A key factor is the variation in individual learning preferences and styles. Type C learners may have unique ways of processing information. While GTM may suit the learning preferences of three learners, it may not be as effective for the two who received a "Fair" rating. This aligns with Bosman & Schuelze's (2018) findings, which highlight that learners tend to achieve better academically when instruction aligns with their learning styles and when these styles are consciously incorporated into their learning strategies.

Furthermore, an assessment was carried out on four (4) learners (Learners 12, 18, 19, and 20) categorized as Type C, utilizing both Explicit SCT and GTM principles. Among this group, learners 19 and 20 secured a rating of 4, signifying a "Good" performance falling within the score range of 3.50-4.49 which corresponds to 70% - 90%, indicating an Advanced learner with adequately appropriate level of directness, politeness, and formality and expressions that are slightly off target-like but still good. In contrast, learners 12 and 18 received a score of 5 or Excellent, signifying an outstanding performance with scores falling within the 4.50-5.00 range which corresponds to 90% - 100%, indicating a Near-native/Proficient learner, which possess an almost perfectly appropriate and effective level of directness, politeness, and formality with target-like expressions.

The varying ratings can be ascribed to differences in the language proficiency levels of the students, significantly influencing their overall performance. Type C learners who attain an "Excellent" rating may exhibit advanced language proficiency, enabling them to surpass other learners in the assessment and consequently secure a higher rating than Type C learners with lower language proficiency.

As shown in Table 2.2, the respondents exhibited an "Excellent" Overall ILP Competence in Expressive speech acts, with mean values spanning from 4.50-5.00. With the findings cited, it is essential to scrutinize the influence of the instructional methods employed in the assessments and consider the characteristics of the learners to discern how these factors contributed to the learners' overall ILP competence rating. The responses in Expressive Speech Acts were categorized based on the types of learners who underwent assessment, including Type A (Fast Learners), Type B (Average learners), and Type C (Slow learners).

Table 2.2. Level of ILP Competence for Expressives (Apologies/Gratitude), Instructional Methods Employed, and Learner Type

Learner	Type of Learner	Method Used	Rating	Description	Mean	Expressive Types	Indicators
21	Type B	Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.21-5.00	Apology	Hey, I'm sorry, I didn't mean to throw the coffee on your table, please forgive me.
22	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	5	Excellent	4.21-5.00	Gratitude	Thank you for helping me move to my new apartment.
23	Type B	Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.21-5.00	Apology	Sorry, my friend, I didn't attend your birthday party, I promise, I'll treat you next time.
24	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.21-5.00	Apology	Brother, I'm sorry, I scratched your car.
25	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)	5	Excellent	4.21-5.00	Gratitude	Sorry, Sir, I didn't pass my assignment on time. I will pass my assignment tomorrow.
26	Type A	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)	5	Excellent	4.21-5.00	Gratitude	Thank you, my little sister, for giving me a present for this day. I appreciate it very much.
27	Type B	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)	5	Excellent	4.21-5.00	Gratitude	I'm sorry, Rafael, for being late, can I just make it up to you by giving you a present or something?
			5	EXCELLENT	4.21-5.00	OVERALL RATING	

Legend:

	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)
	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)
	Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Grammar Translation Method (GTM)
	Grammar Translation Method (GTM)
	Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)

Type A Learner/s

One learner (Learner 26) classified as Type A underwent assessment using the CLT method and attained an "Excellent" level of ILP Competence Rating, falling within the range of 4.50-5.00, corresponding to 90% - 100% ILP continuum level, indicating Near-native/Proficient learner with an almost perfectly appropriate and effective level of directness, politeness, and formality as well as target-like expressions.

Type B Learners

Two learners (Learners 21 and 23), both categorized as Type Bs, were evaluated using the Explicit SCT method, both resulting in an "Excellent" rating of 5, corresponding to 90% - 100% ILP continuum level, indicating Near-native/Proficient learner with an almost perfectly appropriate and effective level of directness, politeness, and formality as well as target-like expressions. Additionally, one learner (Learner 27) within this category was assessed with the CLT method and received a "5" rating, also falling within the range of 4.50-5.00 which has a similar ILP continuum level, descriptors, and type of learner with the former.

Type C Learner/s

Two learners (Learner 22 and 25) categorized as Type Cs underwent assessment employing the GTM, both achieving an "Excellent" rating of 5. Furthermore, Learner 24 was assessed using a combination of the Explicit SCT and GTM, also receiving an "Excellent" rating within the range of 4.50-5.00, all of which corresponds to a 90% - 100% ILP continuum level, indicating a Near-native/Proficient learner with an almost perfectly appropriate and effective level of directness, politeness, and formality and target-like expressions.

The reason for the Overall ILP Competence rating of 5 (Excellent) in Expressive Speech Acts may have a direct application in caregiving, as caregivers often need to convey empathy, understanding, and emotional support to individuals in their care. This real-world relevance would motivate them to excel in these Speech Acts of Expressives.

Caregivers are typically individuals who provide general care and support other people, especially patients, in various aspects of their lives. These caregiving responsibilities encompass emotional support, tending to patients' physical needs such as bathing and dressing, preparing meals and medications, handling financial matters, making decisions related to care, and facilitating communication with

formal health services, as written by (Purwaningsih & Pratama, 2020). Expressives involve conveying emotions and feelings effectively, which aligns with the empathetic communication skills needed in caregiving.

In caregiving, situations frequently demand empathetic and emotionally supportive communication, whether in consoling patients, understanding their requirements, or providing comfort. Expressive communication is highly relevant in this caregiving role, enabling caregivers to connect with patients on an emotional level and offer vital support and reassurance. This aligns seamlessly with the empathetic communication skills needed to fulfill caregivers' responsibilities effectively.

This finding provides an additional perspective to the research by Purwaningsih and Pratama (2020), suggesting that future caregivers, as represented by the respondents, demonstrate competence not only in Directives and Speech Acts but also in the effective use of Expressives.

Table 2.3. Level of ILP Competence for Assertives (Statements/Facts/Opinions), Instructional Methods Employed, and Learner Type

Learner	Type of Learner	Methods Used	Rating	Description	Mean	Assertives Type	Indicators
29	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Opinion	The movie Darna is so funny.
30	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Statement	I learn in Oral Comm., that 90% of the time we use non-verbal communication.
31	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	5	Excellent	4.50-5.00	Fact	The Spaniards colonized the Philippines.
32	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	4	Good	3.50-4.49	Statement	Hi, Sir, I work in Marelco for 4 years.
28	Type C	Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)	1	Very poor	1-1.49	Fact	I disagree in death penalty because no opinion.
			4	GOOD	3.50-4.49.	OVERALL RATING	

Legend:

- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)
- Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)
- Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) and Grammar Translation Method (GTM)
- Grammar Translation Method (GTM)
- Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT)

As illustrated in Table 2.3, the results reveal a spectrum of ILP Competence in Assertive speech acts among the respondents, spanning from "Very Poor" to "Excellent," with mean values ranging between 1-1.49 to 4.50-5.00. Notably, the collective ILP Competence of the students in Assertives is deemed "Good," with a Composite Mean falling within 3.50-4.49. Given these findings, it is crucial to examine the impact of instructional methods employed in the assessments and take into account the characteristics of the learners to understand how these factors contributed to the overall ILP competence rating of the students.

The responses in Assertive Speech Acts were categorized based on the type of learners who underwent assessment, all of which are Type Cs (Slow learners).

Type C Learners

Consequently, the remaining participants were categorized as Type Cs and underwent assessment using a combination of Explicit SCT and GTM.

Three learners (29, 30, and 31) excelled, which were assessed with the principles of Explicit SCT and GTM, achieving a rating of 5, denoting "Excellent," with scores within the range of 4.50-5.00, corresponding to a 90% - 100% ILP continuum level, indicating a Near-native/Proficient learner with an almost perfectly appropriate and effective level of directness, politeness, and formality and target-like expressions. Learner 32, on the one hand, was assessed also with the principles of Explicit SCT and GTM, achieving a rating of 4, indicating "Good," with scores ranging from 3.50-4.49, corresponding to 70% - 90%, indicating an Advanced learner, with an adequately appropriate level of directness, politeness, and formality as well as slightly off target-like expressions but still good. Learner 28 was also assessed with the principles of Explicit SCT and GTM, yet, receiving the lowest rating of 1, signifying "Very Poor," with scores ranging from 1-1.49, corresponding to 10% - 30% ILP continuum level, indicating an Elementary learner type with very difficult to understand expressions and inadequate evidence of accomplishing the intended speech acts.

Despite being classified as Type C learners and undergoing assessment using a combination of Explicit SCT and GTM, the participants

displayed a range of ILP competence ratings. The variability in ratings suggests that individual factors may influence their performance. Notably, one influential factor contributing to this variance in ratings is the learners' varying language proficiency levels.

This was proven in the findings of Tai and Chen (2021), that language proficiency plays a critical role in L2 pragmatics. It also differs among learners, including those classified as slow learners. Better language proficiency may lead to higher assessment performance, while lower proficiency can result in lower ratings. In Second Language Acquisition (SLA) research, proficiency is closely tied to learner strategies, helping compensate for language limitations in tasks.

In sum, the variation in language proficiency highlights the importance of recognizing the uniqueness of each learner, even within the same learner category. It reinforces the idea that one-size-fits-all approaches may not be effective in assessing and nurturing language proficiency, and individual differences should be considered to provide tailored support and instruction.

Interlanguage Pragmatic (ILP) Competence Reinforcement Model based on the Results of the Study

Figure 1. *Interlanguage Pragmatic Competence Reinforcement Model (ILP-CRM) (Malco, 2024)*

Drawing from the study's findings to address the recognized gaps, this ILP Competence Reinforcement Model was formulated. This comprehensive model aims to forge a link between pragmalinguistic input and the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving students' real-world practical application of those inputs. This Model primarily focuses on the development of the said students in using Illocutionary Acts such as Directives, Commissives, and Assertives since it was noted in the findings that the aforementioned students' knowledge on those speech acts needs to be improved.

The ILP Reinforcement Model unfolds through the following stages:

The Level of ILP Competence of the Grade 11-TVL Caregiving students- It starts with the identification of the ILP competence level of the Grade 11-TVL caregiving students through the utilization of the Oral Discourse Completion Task (ODCT).

Factors Affecting their level of ILP Competence – After the ILP competence level identification, three main factors emerged namely (1) Instructional Methods (External Factor) (2) Assessment Methods Used (External Factor), and (3) Learner Attributes/Type (Internal Factor).

Pragmalinguistic Input – The reinforcement of the level of ILP Competence of the students unfolds in this initial stage which combines linguistic and pragmatic information, incorporating language structures such as grammar and vocabulary, alongside their contextual usage for accurate meaning conveyance. It was adapted and modified from the Model of Pragmatic Competence Acquisition of Jernigan (2007) as cited by Norouzian & Eslami (2016). This emphasis was given because Norouzian & Eslami highlighted the persistent neglect of the relationship between grammar and pragmatics in different Communicative Competence Frameworks (CCF). It serves as the foundational layer for learners to hone their language use in diverse social contexts.

It is comprised of two components namely:

Direct Linguistic Encounters - This refers to the students' firsthand experiences with the target language through activities like reading,

listening, or conversing. These interactions expose the Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students to speech acts that need to be given attention based on the result of their ILP Competence assessment such as the Directives, Commissives, and Assertives, setting the foundation for their ILP competence.

Sociocultural Cues - These refer to the cultural underpinnings that influence language use, including norms, values, beliefs, and expectations. Understanding these cues may allow the Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students to anticipate and decipher the intended meanings in various speech acts.

Instructional Methods - Considering that Instructional Methods are one of the factors that affects the level of ILP Competence of the students, this stage recommends the most effective strategies and techniques teachers may continue using to teach and convey information effectively to learners. This stage involves two main pedagogical approaches utilized by Oral Communication Teachers to teach and assess the ILP Competence of their students, to wit:

Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) - One of the two main instructional and assessment methods used by the Oral Communication teacher that was proven most effective to the said learners. It focuses on practical communication, engaging students in real-life conversations to contextualize speech acts.

Grammar Translation Method (GTM) and Explicit Scaffolding Technique (SCT) - The most suitable combination of instructional and assessment methods used by the Oral Communication Teacher in assessing the ILP Competence of his Grade 11-TVLCaregiving students. GTM concentrates on sentence translation between the target and native languages, aiding in understanding sentence structure and meaning in complex speech acts. Explicit SCT, on the one hand, provides structured support to students, gradually reducing assistance as their proficiency improves, fostering independent ILP application.

Pragmatic Filter – This stage involves a cognitive process that enables learners to filter the pragmalinguistic input (Initial Stage), discerning what to integrate or discard, similar to Stephen Krashen's "affective filter" but with a pragmatic focus. This stage was also adapted and modified from the Model of Pragmatic Competence Acquisition of Jernigan (2007) as cited by Norouzian & Eslami (2016).

It includes two distinct components:

Learner's Prior Knowledge and Experience - Recognizes that each student's unique background and language exposure influences how new information is processed. This was inspired by one of the findings of the study that despite learners belonging to the same type and being assessed using a single instructional and assessment method, they gained different ratings on their Level of ILP Competence.

Metapragmatic Awareness - Comprehending the contextual rules and norms of language usage goes beyond mere knowledge of what to say; it encompasses understanding when, why, and how to say it. In the Pragmatic Filter, this aspect was influenced by a study finding that revealed students sometimes neglect the need to adjust their language register appropriately when communicating with individuals that are far in terms of linguistic social distance (i.e., represents the degree of closeness or intimacy experienced by an individual or group in a social network, reflecting the level of trust one group places in another and the extent to which their beliefs align).

Learner's Developing System - This dynamic cognitive structure is based on the Interlanguage Continuum of (Tanvir, 1992). It underpins how learners process, integrate, and utilize language pragmatically in an attempt to conform with the rules of the TL. It signifies the ongoing refinement of language use in sociocultural contexts and encompasses three components, to wit:

Integration of Speech Acts - This is where students integrate various speech acts, such as Directives, Commissives, and Assertives, enhancing their practical application.

Feedback and Reflection - This is where the main role of the Oral Communication teacher takes place considering that continuous external assessment promotes steady growth and refinement of ILP competence.

Practice and Immersion - In an interview with the Oral Communication Teacher, he emphasized the importance of applying language skills in real-world scenarios to enhance the ILP competence of Grade 11-TVLCaregiving students and language learners in general. This involves creating opportunities for them to use language in their respective fields.

Pragmalinguistic Output - The final stage represents how learners articulate and manifest their grasp of the relationship between language forms and functions in communication. It includes two components namely:

Demonstrated ILP Competence - Students should exhibit their proficiency in using illocutionary speech acts (Directives, Commissives, and Assertives) across various contexts.

Learner Confidence and Proficiency - Beyond skill acquisition, a crucial outcome is enhanced confidence, as increased proficiency in ILP competence leads to more confident communication.

Conclusions

Based on the observed findings, the study revealed that Grade 11 TVL-Caregiving students exhibit a high level of proficiency in

Expressive Speech Acts, leading to an impressive Overall ILP Competence Rating of 5, indicating “Excellence.” This exceptional competence can be attributed to their chosen profession as caregivers, which demands effective communication and empathy in expressing thoughts and emotions to provide quality care for individuals in need. Thus, showcasing their aptitude for empathetic and effective communication in their field.

It was also investigated that the learners exposed to a combination of methods such as Explicit SCT and GTM generally achieved "Excellent" ratings. This is because the combination of these methods complements each other. Explicit SCT provides the sociocultural context and meaning, while GTM strengthens the technical and structural aspects of language. Together, they create a holistic learning experience for the said learners.

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